

LITERARY AND AESTHETIC INTERPRETATIONS OF THE IMAGE OF THE MOTHER IN POETRY

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Abstract. The image of the mother and her nature is the main factor determining the perfection of literature and the level of the writer's skill. This means that the creator creates a system of his artistic and philosophical ideas in literature. Since the beginning of literature the thought that the author wants to express is realized as a word, an image, an idea and this phenomenon has become a law. In this regard, the importance and relevance of the topic raised in this article is important.

Keywords. The nature of the poetic image, the relationship between the subject and the idea, social consciousness, diversity of opinions, evaluation criteria.

INTRODUCTION

Motherhood is a concept with different roles and a complicated definition when viewed from the national-cultural, religious-social point of view. Therefore, how does the philosophy that informs mankind about the laws of existence give a definition to this complex concept? In the philosophy representing the place of man in the world and the overall system of the level of worldview, Mother is 1) a concept applied to a person who gave birth to a child; 2) the term applied to a woman who, although she did not give birth to a child, brought him up or made an important contribution to his upbringing; 3) the concept that remains as a symbol of respect for an old woman in the culture of the Uzbek people; 4) it is described as a family member [4.98] who exerts a great influence on the early formation of human spirituality and plays an important role in determining the direction of the worldview

of the generation. At all stages of human history, mothers have performed the role of natural educators . Early education, moral standards, traditions and values characteristic of national mentality are instilled in children through mother. Mother's moral qualities such as modesty, attitude, modesty , orderliness, discipline, patience and contentment are passed from generation to generation. A child will be brought up in the same spirit and qualities as the mother . In this sense, the present day and the future of any state and society are measured by the attitude towards the mother [5.67].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In fiction, the mother theme is a problem that should be studied starting from the ancient mythological roots of human history. Not only in Uzbek, but also in the entire world literature, there are few artists who did not turn to the image of the mother, who is a great creative force. In fiction, especially in poetry, the poetic image of the mother is written as a spiritual aesthetic, national cultural phenomenon. Scholars have expressed their views on the image problem in literary studies since the time of the ancient Greek civilization. Researches were carried out by the Greek philosopher Aristotle, Eastern thinker Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, German scientist Hegel, and modern thinkers Fitrat Cholpon. The image was studied by AT Baumgarten, I. Kant, representatives of Renaissance Europe [10.35]. The issues of artists' ability to create an artistic image have also been thoroughly studied in Uzbek literary studies, and in this regard I. Sultanov, H. Yaqubov, M. Koshjanov, O. Sharafiddinov, S. Mamajonov, N. Karimov, S. Mirvaliyev, B. Nazarov , scientists such as U. Normatov, A. Rasulov and others have created a number of studies [12.35]. Nevertheless, there are few theoretical studies devoted to the image of the

mother in fiction, especially in poetry. The image of the mother has been studied only within the framework of the work of some poets , and it has not been widely analyzed in the case of Uzbek poetry. There is a dissertation on the image of the mother in prose works. IO Dusinbayev's thesis "Mother's image in the work of Otkir Hoshimov" was submitted in 2011 under the guidance of Professor B. Nazarov, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philological Sciences, to receive the degree of candidate of philological sciences. In the dissertation , the scientist summarized the characteristics of the image of the mother in the works of O'tkir Hashimov, the theoretical principles of the writer on the issue of creating a literary aesthetic image, and the issues of nationality, writer's style and skill in character creation.

RESULTS

The image of the mother has always been reflected in poetry as a sacred and divine symbol. He embodies such high qualities as love, loyalty, selflessness, and goodness. In poetry, the image of the mother is interpreted not only as a central figure in the lives of children, but also as a support of the nation and people, a symbol of culture and values. Let's look at the following aspects for a wider coverage of this topic .

DISCUSSION

Mother is a symbol of life and love . In poetry, mother is interpreted as the beginning of life, the main source of living. A mother's love is constant and endless, and it reflects the essence of life. Many poets have described the mother as the great power that created life and allows it to continue. For example, in the poem "Mother" by Erkin Vahidov, mother's love and her kindness are compared to the embrace of

the earth, mother's bosom of nature. In Chingiz Aitmatov's work "The White Ship", the image of the mother is equated with the divine part of nature and life.

Mother is the symbol of patience and devotion. A mother is depicted in poetry as a selfless person who endures the trials of life and is ready to give everything for her children. Every act of a mother, her work for her children became the main theme of the poems. In the poem "Mother" by Abdulla Oripov, the mother is shown as a holy person who fights for the perfection of her children with her every action. Muhammad Yusuf's poem "Mother" expresses the boundlessness of mother's love and its place in life: "Who is dearer than mother in the world? "

mother and nation. Sometimes the image of the mother is interpreted as a symbol of the nation. Mother is associated with high concepts such as motherland, nation, country. Poets describe the mother as the heart of the people, the cultural and spiritual root of the nation. In the epic "Farhad and Shirin" by Alisher Navoi, mother's wisdom and her educational influence are one of the main ideas of the work. Many of Erkin Vahidov's poems are compared to the motherland and its sanctity is highlighted.

Mother and the idea of happiness. Mother is often depicted as the mistress of happiness and dreams. Poets cannot imagine a person without mother's love as truly happy. A mother's smile, her prayers and wishes are shown as the main source of happiness in children's lives.

For example, in Movludabonu Imomnazarova's poem "Mother who owes happiness to us", the mother is expressed as a person who will achieve happiness in the future due to her hard work and dedication.

You don't know, mother, one day,

The joys are many for us.

You will be the mistress of the castle of dreams ,

Mother owes us happiness...

In this poem by Movludabonu Imomnazarova, the image of mother is described with high respect and gratitude. In the poem, the mother is expressed not only as the support of the family, but also as a symbol of great blessing, happiness and goodness for humanity. When analyzing the text, the following aspects can be distinguished:

Time and space are reflected in the poem as relative concepts. Mother's difficult times in her life, her sacrifices for the family and her visions of future happy days are told through time.

Surely you will wear a crown of honor,

I will build a tower for you in heaven.

You will always be by my side ,

Mother owes us happiness...

Verses like It is a hopeful and aspirational image of the future . The hardships, work and dedication of a mother's life are represented through the past and present tense. It is hoped that these hardships will be replaced by joy and happiness in the future.

A mother here is filled with a divine feeling not only for her children, but for all mankind. Throughout the poem, the idea of a debt to the mother is repeated, thereby giving a deeper meaning to the role of the mother in human life: the mother is the mistress of happiness and dreams. In the verses " You will be the mistress of the palace of dreams , the mother who owes happiness to us", the mother is shown as a symbol of future happiness. The verse "I will build a tower for you in heaven" expresses the divine position of the mother, that she is the gate of heaven for her

children. The poem repeatedly emphasizes the feeling of debt to the mother. This feeling is described in two ways. A child's gratitude to the mother: In the verse "We give thanks to Allah from the heart", gratitude is expressed to the Creator for the presence of the mother. The words "Mother who owes happiness to us" describe that a mother's work does not go in vain, and her children return her happiness and attention.

Usman Azim's Poems are enriched with sincerity and goodness. Emotional Intensity: Every desire and intention related to the mother is highly expressed. For example, one can feel the boundless love of the poet for his mother through the lines " I will bury you in happiness and joy, this desire is the only one in my heart". The poem is written in a hopeful spirit from beginning to end. Images such as the disappearance of loneliness and sadness and the priority of health and happiness emphasize this.

This poem by Movludabonu Imomnazarova is dedicated to describing the great image of mother through the change of time and space . The poem expresses a person's debt to the mother , gratitude and love from the heart. At the same time, the importance of the mother in the lives of her children and her equating with heaven embodies modern and immortal ideas.

Mother is also a phenomenon related to time and space. Time and space are used in literature with the concept of chronotope, which also gives the tones of divinity. Because the owner of time and space is the only Creator. Many poets have glorified the mother as the miracle of the Creator on earth. Mother's prayers, love and actions are depicted as divine protection for children. Erkin Vahidov's poem "Mother's Spirit" describes a mother's prayer as a divine power for children. In the

works of Turkish poets Jalaluddin Rumi and Yunus Emre, mother is recognized as a symbol of spiritual purity and divine love.

In poetry, the image of mother is described as the greatest value for humanity. Poets glorify love, devotion, patience, happiness and divinity through mother. The image of the mother is not only an artistic interpretation, but also embodies a universality close to the inner feelings of each person. This confirms that the image of the mother is eternal and immortal in poetry. In the poem "Letter to my mother", the chronotope - that is, the artistic harmony of time and space - is closely related to the poet's mental state and inner experiences. Analyzing the chronotope, the role of the image of space and time in the illumination of the hero's feelings and their mutual harmony is evident in the poem.

In the poem "Letter to my mother", the autumn season and the silence of the night are interpreted as central images of time and space. This season and state expresses a person's deeper feelings of loneliness, memory and inner anguish.

Time: Autumn and late night

"Sooner or later,

Mist falls on the gardens"[12.14]

Autumn season represents the complex periods of life, ending and new beginning at the same time. Late night creates favorable conditions for inner silence and philosophical thoughts. This image of time serves to emphasize the longing and loneliness of the poet for his mother.

Location: Window and a nightstand

"Pressing a wet hand against the window,

A dream when Kuzak sleeps at night"[10.11].

The window represents the boundary between two worlds for the poet: the outer world (autumn, frost, rain) and the inner world (imagination, emotions). This image intensifies the inner pain of the poet towards his mother.

In the poem, the chronotope plays a central role in revealing the feelings of the lyrical hero. Time and space are used as a means of reflecting the poet's state of mind. "I am the loneliest of the lonely." The coldness of autumn and late night intensifies the hero's inner anguish and loneliness. These feelings are softened by thinking about the mother, but not completely gone.

"It is clear that I cry when I remember you." Memory and longing are enhanced by autumn and rain. The image of nature (rain, rain) more vividly reflects the suffering and love in the poet's heart.

time and space in the poem serves to deepen the understanding of the hero's mental experiences. Autumn season and late night are used as a metaphorical tool that illuminates the inner state of the poet. Spatial images such as windows and rain represent the border between the outer and inner worlds and illuminate the love for the mother.

The chronotope of the poem - autumn and night, rain and snow - provides a deep philosophical interpretation of human life and feelings. The cold and quiet image of nature further enhances the inner anguish and longing of the poet. Thus, the chronotope enriches the content of the poem and increases its emotional impact.

CONCLUSION

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